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POTENTIAL AND PROSPECTS OF USING ALTERNATIVE FUELS IN PISTON ENGINES OF HYBRID POWER SYSTEMS

Abstract. This article examines the advantages and prospects of using such fuels as biodiesel, hydrogen, and methanol. Mathematical modeling of piston engine operation with various fuel types has been conducted. Numerical methods were applied to analyze combustion processes and evaluate the performance of alternative fuels. The results demonstrate the potential for reducing energy consumption and harmful emissions.

Keywords: biodiesel, hydrogen, methanol, engine, numerical methods.

Introduction. Modern internal combustion piston engines, which are widely used in vehicles and industrial power systems, primarily run on fossil fuels-oil, natural gas, and coal. Burning these fuels results in substantial emissions of carbon dioxide (CO_2), nitrogen oxides (NO_x), and particulates, which contribute to global warming, acid rain, and other environmental issues. The increasing number of vehicles exacerbates these negative impacts, underscoring the need for more environmentally safe technologies [1].

Research points to the advantages of alternative fuels over traditional ones. For instance, biodiesel exhibits higher environmental performance and lower CO_2 emissions, while hydrogen releases only water vapor upon combustion, minimizing climate impact [1]. However, each fuel type has technical limitations that must be addressed for stable piston engine operation.

The objective of this study is to analyze the advantages and prospects of using alternative fuels in piston engines within a hybrid power system and to perform a mathematical analysis of the combustion process of alternative fuels in such engines. The primary parameters considered in modeling include cylinder pressure and temperature, fuel composition and properties, reaction kinetics, and heat exchange between the cylinder walls and the working medium. The task is to create a mathematical model that allows for predicting the combustion efficiency and environmental performance of various alternative fuels [2].

Three main groups of equations are used for modeling the combustion process: mass balance, energy, and chemical reaction equations. When burning alternative fuels, it is essential to account for the mass balance of each component of the fuel mixture and the combustion products. The mass balance equation can be expressed as:

$$\frac{d}{dt}(\rho V) + \nabla \cdot (\rho u V) = \sum \dot{m}_{in} - \sum \dot{m}_{out}, \quad (1)$$

where ρ – density of the working mixture; $\nabla \cdot (\rho u)$ – divergence of mass density flow; V – cylinder volume; u – speed; $\dot{m}_{in}, \dot{m}_{out}$ – mass flow of input and output components.

For describing heat transfer and determining the amount of energy released during combustion, the energy equation is applied:

$$\frac{d}{dt}(E) = \dot{Q} - \dot{W}, \quad (2)$$

where E – internal energy of the system; \dot{Q} – heat added to the system; \dot{W} – work done by the gas.

Heat losses through the cylinder walls and the efficiency of heat transfer to the working mixture are also considered. The combustion of alternative fuels, such as hydrogen or biodiesel, involves a series of chemical reactions. These reactions are mostly described by a system of differential equations.

$$\frac{dC_i}{dt} R_i(C_1, C_2, \dots, C_n), \quad (3)$$

where C_i – concentration of the i -th substance; R_i – reaction rate for each component.

In the case of hydrogen, the main reaction is described by a formula $2H_2 + O_2 \rightarrow 2H_2O$, that ensures high combustion efficiency and minimal harmful emissions. To achieve optimal performance of the hybrid power unit, numerical modeling methods are used, allowing for the evaluation of the efficiency and environmental impact of alternative fuel combustion under various parameters. The optimization of the fuel mixture involves finding the optimal air-to-fuel ratio that will provide maximum energy efficiency and minimal levels of harmful emissions.

$$ER = \frac{m_{air}}{m_{fuel}}, \quad (4)$$

where ER – air/fuel ratio; m_{air} – air mass; m_{fuel} – mass of fuel.

Boundary conditions for temperature and pressure are set depending on the type of fuel and engine design [3]. As part of the study, we will create a model that describes the combustion processes, fuel consumption, and harmful emissions for a hybrid power unit using a piston engine. To achieve this, we will examine the fuel combustion energy equation:

$$Q = m \cdot H_u \cdot \eta \quad (5)$$

where Q – is the total thermal energy released during combustion (J); m – is the mass of fuel (kg); H_u – is the lower heating value of the fuel (J/kg); η – is the combustion efficiency, which accounts for heat losses and incomplete fuel combustion. Fuel consumption (Specific Fuel Consumption, SFC):

$$SFC = \frac{m}{P \cdot t}, \quad (6)$$

where SFC – is the specific fuel consumption (kg/kW·h); P – is the engine power (kW); t – the operating time on the selected fuel (h).

The emission level can be calculated as a function of the air excess ratio λ and combustion temperature. For example, the CO_2 emission level can be described as follows [4]:

$$E_{CO_2} = k \cdot \frac{m \cdot C}{M}, \quad (7)$$

where: E_{CO_2} – the mass of emissions CO_2 ; k – coefficient depending on complete combustion; C – carbon content in fuel; M – fuel molecular weight.

Figure 1 – Comparison of combustion efficiency, specific fuel consumption, and CO_2 emission levels for different types of alternative fuels in piston engines

In Figure 1, graph 1 should indicate the relationship between combustion efficiency and temperature, graph 2 should show specific fuel consumption (SFC) as a function of engine power, and graph 3 should illustrate CO_2 and NO_x emission levels as a function of the air excess ratio.

Conclusions. The study results indicate that the use of hydrogen provides zero CO_2 emissions, high fuel efficiency, and improved performance metrics, making it ideal for environmentally oriented applications. Methanol, due to its properties, offers a balance between environmental friendliness and cost, while biodiesel serves as a reliable option for engines where fuel stability and high energy density are crucial.

The adoption of alternative fuels significantly reduces greenhouse gas emissions, improves fuel efficiency, and lowers operational costs, which are crucial factors under modern environmental regulations [5]. Future research prospects lie in enhancing existing mathematical models for more accurate simulation of alternative fuel combustion processes and a comprehensive analysis of hybrid power unit characteristics.

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